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**LEGAL FRAMEWORKS, NATIONAL SECURITY, AND
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**10-The Dynamics of Public-Private
Interaction in Advancing Sustainable
Development Through Investment Strategies
and Administration. By Myroslav Buryk and
others. p. 198.**

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**LEGAL FRAMEWORKS, NATIONAL SECURITY, AND
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PREPARED**

**CENTER FOR LAW AND POLITICAL RESEARCH – DENMARK
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**THE DYNAMICS OF PUBLIC-PRIVATE
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ABSTRACT

The article explores interaction between government and business in pursuing sustainable development through joint investment strategies. Its aim is to develop a model of partnership to achieve economic effects while adhering to sustainability principles. The methodology combines quantitative and qualitative approaches, including structural analysis, a matrix method, and elements of game theory to assess

optimal strategies. Findings show that direct investment, public-private partnership, innovation-oriented, institutional, sectoral, and anti-crisis strategies generate synergy when cooperation intensifies. Econometric modeling under various scenarios identifies conditions for optimal strategy choice, considering risks and financial stability. The study offers recommendations for joint projects fostering sustainable development and proposes an adaptable model for national and regional programs in Ukraine, integrating risk, sustainability, and macroeconomic factors.

Keywords: *effectiveness of public policy, public finance, public-private partnership, local government, local development strategy.*

1- INTRODUCTION

Today, Ukraine's economy is undergoing profound transformations, which necessitates the search for effective mechanisms to stimulate sustainable development, in particular through the intensification of investment activity based on strategic interaction between government agencies and the business environment. In the new conditions of global competition and high technological dynamics, it is investment strategies developed and implemented jointly by the public and private sectors that should become a tool for the formation of a new type of economy focused on innovation, energy efficiency, high levels of added value and sustainable development.¹

The relevance of the study is determined by the need to move from fragmented and short-term investment decisions to systemic strategies based on long-term partnerships between public institutions and private companies. Despite the implementation of a number of national programs and the attraction of foreign capital, Ukraine still lacks coordination of investment policy and a coherent model of strategic interaction between the public and private sectors. Existing investment projects are often narrowly focused on a single industry or raw materials, which limits their ability to bring about structural changes in the economy and high growth rates.² Thus, an

¹ Aboelazm, K. S., Tawakol, F., Dganni, K. M., & AlFil, N. Z. (2024). Public-private partnership: A new policy to ameliorate the quality of public utility services to the public. *Journal of Lifestyle and SDGs Review*, 4(4), e02509. <https://doi.org/10.47172/2965-730X.SDGsReview.v4.n04.pe02509>

² Pajak, K., Omelyanenko, V., Makedon, V., Shevchenko, V., & Ovcharenko, I. (2020). Raising the level of financial security of the enterprise based on the basic risks differentiation. *Journal of Security and Sustainability Issues*, 10(1), 115–130. [https://doi.org/10.9770/jssi.2020.10.1\(9\)](https://doi.org/10.9770/jssi.2020.10.1(9));

Mamchur, R., Minochkina, O., Ianushevych, I., & Khrystenko, L. (2023). Optimization of operational and financial risks of conducting business activities under the conditions of changes and sustainable development. *Economic Affairs*, 68(1s), 91–98. <https://doi.org/10.46852/0424-2513.1s.2023.11>

urgent scientific and practical problem is the development of effective tools for strategic interaction between the state and business in the investment sphere, which would form a holistic architectonics of sustainable development for the state.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

The studies by McCaffrey and Poitiers³ and Yelnikova et al.⁴ focus on the analysis of investment as a holistic set of resources and actions carried out within the framework of external conditions and limited available resources. The authors emphasize the systemic nature of investment, covering all stages of resource investment, taking into account the institutional environment. However, the study is limited to a general resource logic and does not offer specific approaches to harmonizing the interests of public and private entities in the context of sustainable development.

Further, Baffo et al.⁵ and Kulinich and Obushok⁶ focus on the concept of the life cycle of investment activity, identifying three main stages: pre-investment, investment and operational, which is the basis for step-by-step monitoring of investment performance. At the same time, this model does not sufficiently address the mechanisms for involving business in the formation of long-term sustainable development strategies, especially in the context of asymmetry of access to information and capital at the state level.

Beisengaliyev and Kossymbayeva,⁷ Belu Manescu,⁸ Jaźwiński⁹ have made a significant contribution to the development of the concept of public investment strategies, focusing on the multiplier effects of such initiatives: modernization of

³ McCaffrey, C., & Poitiers, N. F. (2024). *Instruments of economic security* (Bruegel Working Paper). Bruegel. https://www.bruegel.org/system/files/2024-05/WP%2012%202024_0.pdf

Meuleman, L. (2021). Public administration and governance for the SDGs: Navigating between change and stability. *Sustainability*, 13(11), 5914. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13115914>

⁴ Yelnikova, Y., Makarenko, I., Artemenko, A., & Gorodetska, M. (2022). Investigation of socially responsible investment strategies taxonomy. *European Journal of Management Issues*, 30(3), 177–186. <https://doi.org/10.15421/192216>

⁵ Baffo, I., Leonardi, M., D'Alberti, V., & Petrillo, A. (2024). Optimizing public investments: A sustainable economic, environmental, and social investment multicriteria decision model (SEESIM). *Regional Science Policy & Practice*, 16, Article 100140. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rspp.2024.100140>

⁶ Kulinich, T. V., & Obushok, I. I. (2024). Investment strategies for economic growth of Ukraine in global context. *Skhidna Yevropa: Ekonomika, Biznes ta Upravlinnia*, (43), 99–106. <https://doi.org/10.32782/easterneurope.43-16>

⁷ Beisengaliyev, B., & Kossymbayeva, S. I. (2025). Government roles and public investment strategies in economic development. *SHS Web of Conferences*, 212, Article 04061. <https://doi.org/10.1051/shsconf/202521204061>

⁸ Belu Manescu, C. (2024). The planning of public investments in EU Member States: Long-term strategy, selection and budgeting issues (European Economy Discussion Paper 213). Directorate-General for Economic and Financial Affairs, European Commission. <https://doi.org/10.2765/453371>

⁹ Jaźwiński, I. (2023). Economic security threats: Determinants of state functioning and economic policy. *Przegląd Strategiczny*, 16, 77–88. <https://doi.org/10.14746/ps.2023.1.6>

enterprises, creation of jobs, and improvement of the quality of life. However, the concept needs to be refined in terms of integrating business into the formation of regional priorities, as the mechanisms for dividing functions between the state and the business sector remain unclear.

Holovnia et al.¹⁰ and Sinaj et al.¹¹ define investment projects (IPs) as a tool of state regulation implemented through a system of goals, criteria, and resource redistribution and highlight the issues of equity in investment distribution and territorial balance. At the same time, the issue of adapting investment strategies to different socio-economic realities of the regions, in particular, the mechanisms of private capital participation in achieving socially significant results, remains unresolved.

Oerlemans and Langenhuijzen¹² and Strelcow et al.¹³ provide a critical assessment of centralized approaches to IP implementation, justifying the feasibility of implementing such projects at the level of public administration structures with the active participation of private investors. These searches open up opportunities for better adaptation to the real needs of the region, but there is a challenge to ensure institutional trust between the public and private sectors, as well as to maintain focus on long-term sustainable development goals.

Meuleman¹⁴ emphasizes in his approach the strategic nature of the IP, focused on the interests of not only the state and business, but also the regional society. This resolution strengthens the requirements for transparency, accountability, and inclusiveness of the investment process, but the researchers do not present or justify a unified methodology for assessing the integrated effect of such multilateral interaction. Researchers of the level of Bokovets et al.¹⁵ declare that investment should be prioritized in the context of state development and the coordinate system of strategic objectives. At the same time, the problem of integrating non-financial aspects of sustainable development, such as energy efficiency, innovation orientation, and

¹⁰ Holovnia, Y., Kotsiurubenko, G., Husiatynskyi, M., & Martyniuk, I. (2019). Methodology for determining the factors that affect the current state of implementation of investment strategies in public administration. *International Journal of Engineering and Advanced Technology*, 8(6), 4484–4487. <https://doi.org/10.35940/ijeat.F8996.088619>

¹¹ Sinaj, Z., Vela, F., & Shaip, G. (2024). National policy instruments for restoring the post-war economy and factors of sustainability of the Ukrainian economy. *Development Management*, 23(2), 49–55. <https://doi.org/10.57111/devt/2.2024.49>

¹² Oerlemans, J.-J., & Langenhuijzen, S. (2024). Balancing national security and privacy: Examining the use of commercially available information in OSINT practices. *International Journal of Intelligence and CounterIntelligence*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08850607.2024.2387850>

¹³ Strelcow, W., Padafet, Iu., & Ulyanchenko, Yu. (2023). Approaches for assessing the public administration activities in the field of ensuring sustainability. *IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science*, 1150(1), 012017. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1755-1315/1150/1/012017>

¹⁴ Meuleman, L. (2021). *Id.*

¹⁵ Bokovets, V., Moroz, O., & Kraevska, A. (2024). Innovation and investment perspective activities in Ukraine. *Innovation and Sustainability*, 4(2), 11–19. <https://doi.org/10.31649/ins.2024.2.11.19>

environmental safety, remains on the periphery of its concept. In parallel, Wijaya et al.¹⁶ outline their range of investment support from the state: equity participation, state guarantees, grants, and soft loans. They provide an interdisciplinary perspective for analyzing support instruments, but ignore the problems of monitoring the effectiveness of their implementation in the context of complex institutional interaction between the state and business structures.

Thus, despite the wide coverage of the issues of investment cooperation between the state and business, there are a number of gaps in research. Further developments are needed in the following areas: 1) building models of multilevel interaction based on the interests of the state, business and civil society; 2) formalizing mechanisms for assessing the synergy between state support instruments and entrepreneurial activity. The absence of a single conceptual approach to the integration of investment strategies into sustainable development policy creates space for new interdisciplinary research.

The aim of the article is to study the formats for establishing investment cooperation between state and business structures to obtain joint economic results, taking into account the requirements of sustainable development.

3. METHOD

The research methodology is based on a combination of quantitative and qualitative methods. The logical-structural method created a decomposition of investment strategies (direct investment, PPP, innovation, institutional, sectoral, anti-crisis) into key elements: tools, roles of the state and business, and expected economic effects. The method systematizes the level relationships between the country's sustainable development goals, economic conditions, and investment results, creating a conceptual framework for evaluation in the format of the research objective.

The main source of data was the analytical database "Private Participation in Infrastructure (PPI)" database of the World Bank, which contains information on public investment projects in the G20 countries. The quantitative analysis included the processing of data on the volume of investment in projects using statistical generalization and forecasting methods. The matrix approach and elements of game theory, in particular the Bernoulli-Laplace criterion, were used to model investment interaction to select the optimal strategy in an uncertain economic environment. Cash flow forecasting for the proposed projects is based on a scenario approach with parallel calculation of investment costs.

4. RESULTS

¹⁶ Wijaya, F., Waspada, I., & Sari, M. (2024). A systematic literature review of investment strategies in perfect capital markets: Insights from the PRISMA framework. *International Journal of Entrepreneurship and Sustainability Studies*, 4(2), 47–65. <https://doi.org/10.31098/ijeass.v4i2.2813>

4.1. SPECIFIC FEATURES AND EFFECTS OF INVESTMENT STRATEGIES IN THE INTERACTION OF STATE AND BUSINESS STRUCTURES

Authors propose to understand an investment strategy in the context of interaction between the public and private sectors as a systematically organized, conceptually coordinated action plan that defines long-term goals, priorities, directions, tools and forms of mobilization and allocation of investment resources, taking into account the interests of the state, market needs and strategic business guidelines.¹⁷ Based on the logical and structural generalization of the basic investment strategies in business, there will be made additions and their integration for the sphere of the state format of interaction.

1) The direct investment strategy involves direct investment of state or corporate resources in the capital of enterprises, industries or infrastructure facilities of strategic importance for economic development. It can be implemented through national investment funds, specialized agencies, state development banks, as well as through direct agreements between the government and business structures. In the format of this model, authors define that the state plays the role of both an investor and a guarantor of stability, ensuring transparency of procedures, institutional support and minimizing risks.¹⁸

2) The strategy of public-private partnership (PPP) is based on long-term cooperation between the state and business in the implementation of infrastructure, social or production projects, in which the public sector provides regulatory, organizational or financial support, while business assumes management, operation or financing functions. PPPs take the form of concessions, leases, easements, co-financing, and joint ventures.¹⁹

3) The innovation-oriented investment strategy is based on the principle of directing investments into research and development, high-tech production, and digitalization of management processes, which aims to ensure the structural modernization of the economy and its technological renewal. In this strategy, the state acts not only as a source of funding but also as an agent of innovation policy, creating an ecosystem of business support. Cooperation with business in this area allows for effective commercialization of scientific developments and reduction of barriers between science and production.

¹⁷ G20. (2025). *Revised discussion paper: South Africa G20 presidency – Principles for an inclusive and sustainable global economy*. G20. <https://g20.org/wp-content/uploads/2025/04/Revised-Discussion-Paper-South-Africa-G20.pdf>

¹⁸ Sedovs, E., Volkova, T., & Ludviga, I. (2025). Sustainable development and strategic management: What is on the horizon in our nonergodic world research? *Sustainable Futures*, 9, Article 100414. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sftr.2024.100414>

¹⁹ Iguchi, C., Giroud, A., Zhao, S., & Zhang, S. (2025). International business and sustainable development in Asia: Opportunities and challenges for firms and countries. *Asian Business & Management*, 24(1), 1–24. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41291-025-00297-6>

4) The strategy of institutional investment support envisages the creation and improvement of regulatory, legal, administrative and fiscal conditions that ensure a favorable investment environment. In this context, the state acts as an institutional facilitator, creating legislative guarantees for investor protection, simplifying licensing procedures, introducing electronic services and deregulation measures.²⁰ In cooperation with business, a unified investment front is formed, where public and private entities jointly identify barriers to development and mechanisms to overcome them.

5) The strategy of stimulating sectoral investment is based on a selective approach to capital allocation, focusing on priority sectors of the national economy capable of generating high levels of added value, technological breakthroughs or export potential. Such a strategy implies that the state acts as a strategic analyst and coordinator, providing sectoral expertise, forecasting, and promoting the concentration of investments in selected areas (sectors) of the national economy.²¹

6) The anti-crisis investment strategy, in turn, becomes relevant in times of economic turbulence, armed conflicts or global crises, when it is necessary to support critical sectors, restore infrastructure, stabilize employment and maintain investment attractiveness. In this format, the state resorts to anti-crisis packages, guarantee programs, and international technical assistance, while businesses implement strategies for survival, cost optimization, and production re-profiling. (Table 1).

Table 1. Evaluation of individual effects of investment strategies in ensuring interaction between government agencies and business

Strategy	Main instruments	Role of the state	Role of business	Expected effects
1. Direct investment	National funds, development banks, agreements	Investor, guarantor of stability	Contractor, co-investor	Multiplier effect, jobs
2. Public-private partnerships	Concessions, leasing, co-financing	Regulator, co-financier	Management, operation	Innovation, flexibility, efficiency
3. Innovation-oriented	R&D funding, technology parks, hubs	Agent of innovation policy	Commercialization of development	Technological renewal, modernization

²⁰ Magliacani, M. (2023). How the sustainable development goals challenge public management: Action research on the cultural heritage of an Italian smart city. *Journal of Management and Governance*, 27, 987–1015. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10997-022-09652-7>

²¹ Davidenko, L., Titkov, A., Sherimova, N., & Beisembina, A. (2025). Economic aspects of sustainable development: Ecobranding in manufacturing enterprises from Kazakhstan. *Sustainability*, 17(1), 36. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su17010036>

Strategy	Main instruments	Role of the state	Role of business	Expected effects
			nts	
4. Institutional support	Legislative guarantees, deregulation	Institutional facilitator	Identification of barriers	Favorable investment environment
5. Stimulation of sectoral investment	Sectoral expertise, forecasting	Strategic coordinator	Investor in priority sectors	High added value, exports
6. Anti-crisis measures	Guarantee programs, technical assistance	Stabilization coordinator	Optimization, re-profiling	Economic recovery, stability

Source: Petroia and Banu,²² Budnyk et al.²³

An example of this format of projects is investments in infrastructure development, including transport, energy, and telecommunications networks, which are of great importance for ensuring economic stability and improving the quality of life of the population.²⁴ Here are selected data from a number of countries that demonstrate the prevalence and sustainability of investment relations between businesses and government agencies (Table 2).

Table 2. Investment volumes in public-private partnership projects in the leading countries of the world (2019-2023), billion USD USD

Country	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
Argentina	1,500	0,800	1,200	1,400	1,595
Australia	8,500	6,200	8,800	9,200	8,700
Brazil	18,600	7,733	15,700	17,400	8,200

²² Petroia, A. C., & Banu, A. (2025). Public investments and their role in promoting state strategies – Case of the Republic of Moldova. SSRN. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.5283334>

²³ Budnyk, V., Vasyliieva, N., Artemenko, A., Shcherbak, V., & Kapelista, I. (2025). Public-private partnerships as a catalyst for sustainable development. *Journal of Lifestyle and SDGs Review*, 5(2), e03635. <https://doi.org/10.47172/2965730X.SDGsReview.v5.n02.pe03635>

²⁴ Makedon, V. V., Valikov, V. P., & Koshlyak, Ye. Ye. (2020). The global labor market in the coordinates of the digital economy. *Academic Review*, 1(52), 91–104. <https://doi.org/10.32342/2074-5354-2020-1-52-9>

Canada	7,200	5,500	7,500	7,800	7,600
China	26,300	6,285	10,600	30,300	40,400
France	6,300	4,800	6,500	6,700	6,400
Germany	5,200	4,000	5,400	5,600	5,300
India	7,600	5,251	7,700	11,900	7,000
Indonesia	0,372	0,900	1,200	1,500	1,762
Japan	6,100	4,700	6,300	6,500	6,200
Mexico	3,000	4,269	1,100	2,100	0,245
SOUTH AFRICA	0,972	0,800	1,000	1,960	1,044
Turkey	1,000	2,500	9,400	2,800	0,434
US DOLLARS (IN THOUSANDS)	10,500	8,000	11,000	11,500	10,800

Source: World Bank, Public-Private Partnership Group²⁵

Thus, the defining parameters of such projects are their compliance with the state strategies of socio-economic development, the justification of capital expenditures, the number of jobs created, and the effect on the state budget.

4.2. FORMATS OF PROJECT INTERACTION BETWEEN GOVERNMENT AND BUSINESS STRUCTURES IN THE REALITIES OF UKRAINE

To ensure sustainable socio-economic development of Ukraine, it is important to develop systemic measures that cover all sectors of the economy and social sphere and create conditions for a qualitative transition to new stages of economic development. The main purpose of state participation in investment projects is to develop the basic sectors of the economy, such as energy, transport and infrastructure, which can have a significant impact on other sectors of the economy. With the help of such a mechanism, government agencies can ensure the predictability of project cash flows, taking into account the tax preferences provided (Figure 1).

²⁵ World Bank, Public-Private Partnership Group. (2023). *Private participation in infrastructure (PPI) project database*. World Bank. <https://ppi.worldbank.org/en/ppi>

An equally important tool to support investment activity is the provision of state guarantees, which helps businesses, especially those implementing high-risk investment projects, to access cheaper financing. In particular, companies that have difficulty obtaining loans from commercial banks due to high risk can apply for state guarantees to fulfill their obligations to financial institutions. In this case, the state assumes part of the risks, which allows investors to obtain loans at lower interest rates, thereby reducing the cost of lending for businesses.²⁶

This practice helps the state to avoid direct financing of projects through the budget, as risks are distributed among government agencies, banks, and businesses. Thus, state guarantees contribute to a more efficient allocation of financial resources, reducing expenditures from the state budget, while increasing access to necessary financing for enterprises (Figure 2).

The problem of investment financing is one of the most important aspects when deciding on the implementation of investment projects in Ukraine, as it is the availability and accessibility of financing that determines the possibility of their implementation. All investment projects are usually associated with a certain time lag between costs and return on investment, which creates the need to choose appropriate forms of financing. One of these forms is project financing, which is a fairly common mechanism for implementing large investment initiatives in international practice.²⁷

²⁶ Shynkarenko, S. (2024). Interaction between the state and development companies: Ways to integrate international experience in Ukraine. *Scientific Herald of Chernivtsi University. Geography*, (849), 143–153. <https://doi.org/10.31861/geo.2024.849.143-153>

²⁷ Slawotsky, J. (2024). Conceptualizing national security in an era of great power rivalry: Implications for international economic law. *East Asia*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12140-024-09434-y>

Figure 1. Scheme of managing investment strategies for sustainable development through cooperation between government and business structures

Source: developed by the authors

Figure 2. Transformation management system through the interaction of state and business structures through joint investment projects

Source: developed by the authors

Authors define the essence of project financing in the field of targeted lending to the borrower for the implementation of an investment project, with future cash flows generated in the course of the project implementation as collateral for such financing. It should be noted that unlike traditional financing, which uses physical assets as collateral, project financing may have a significantly higher level of risk due to the lack of physical collateral, which may increase financial risks for investors, however, future

revenues generated from the project may be the basis for securing financing in the future (Table 2).²⁸

Table 2. Evaluation of parameters of investment strategies in the interaction of state and business structures to ensure sustainable development of Ukraine

Parameter	Project investment strategy	Corporate investment strategy	Commentary
Risk of failure to fulfill obligations	Low	High	As part of project investment, which is actively used in Ukraine to implement strategic sustainable development initiatives, such as infrastructure restoration or green energy development, it is possible to include additional conditions for protection against default, which contributes to effective interaction between the state and business
Risk of loss of investment resources	Low	High	In project investment based on cooperation between government agencies and businesses, the property created or acquired within the project, such as critical infrastructure, is used as collateral, which reduces risks for investors and helps to attract resources for sustainable development
Risk of project implementation delays	Low	High	Project investment in Ukraine, for example, in the framework of public-private partnerships for the modernization of transport networks, often involves clearly defined implementation schedules, which ensures stability and predictability in the interaction between the state and business
Flexibility in	High	Low	In project investment, which is used to

²⁸ Pasinovich, I., & Myskiv, G. (2023). Ukrainian context of sustainable development and the role of business in its achievement. *Regional Science Policy & Practice*, 15(1), 161–181. <https://doi.org/10.1111/rsp3.12619>

restructuring investment resources			finance innovative or environmental initiatives, the state and business can jointly adapt the capital structure by converting debt into equity, which contributes to the sustainability of projects and their alignment with sustainable development goals
Impact of the regulatory environment	Low	High	Project investment in Ukraine is regulated only within a specific project, such as in the renewable energy sector, which simplifies interaction between government agencies and businesses, while corporate investment covers a wider range of company activities, making coordination more difficult
Efficiency of attracting external investment	High	Low	Project investment, which is actively used to attract international partners to implement strategic projects in Ukraine, such as digitalization or environmental initiatives, provides transparency and predictability, which increases investor confidence and promotes sustainable development
Synergistic effect of interaction	High	Moderate	Project investment creates a platform for close cooperation between the state and business, for example, in the implementation of infrastructure projects, which helps to pool resources, competencies and goals aimed at ensuring the economic, social and environmental stability of Ukraine

Source: developed by the authors

Thus, authors note that government and business structures should interact to ensure the successful attraction of project financing for the implementation of investment projects.²⁹ In the case of Ukraine, this type of interaction is necessary because it is state support in the form of guarantees or partial financing that can reduce

²⁹ Alekseieva, K., Maletych, M., Ptashchenko, O., Baranova, O., & Buryk, Z. (2023). State business support programmes in wartime conditions. *Economic Affairs*, 68(1s), 231–242. <https://doi.org/10.46852/04242513.1s.2023.26>

risks for the private sector, simplifying access to the necessary resources for business modernization and expansion.

4.3. MODELING STRATEGIES FOR INVESTMENT COOPERATION BETWEEN THE STATE AND BUSINESS STRUCTURES IN UKRAINE

In the proposed approach, the formation of a portfolio of real investments should be based on the principles of interaction between public and private entities, where the key role is played by assessing changes in the financial structure of the business entity as a result of the inclusion of a particular investment decision.

Stage one. The first stage of this approach is to determine the key indicators of financial stability of the business structure using reporting data, which allows to assess the initial state of the system before the implementation of the investment strategy. The next step is to forecast financial statements for several periods, modeling the inclusion of each of the potential investment options in the target portfolio.³⁰ The forecast will provide opportunities to identify how the financial condition of the business structure will change, taking into account the chosen strategic directions.

The third step is to build an analytical matrix that allows comparing the results and diagnosing the feasibility of including specific projects in the investment strategy, taking into account the goals of sustainable development X^i

$$X^i = \begin{vmatrix} X_{11}^{ip} & X_{12}^{ip} & \dots & X_{1k}^{ip} \end{vmatrix} \quad (1)$$

- X_{1j}^{ip} - indicator of the state of the j -th indicator for the i -th evaluated project in the P -th period;
- i - perspective investment project ($i=1,2,\dots,l$);
- P - period ($p=1,2,\dots,n$); j - indicator of the financial condition of the business structure ($j=1,2,\dots,k$).

Next, a generalized indicator of the financial condition of the business structure should be calculated, taking into account the i of the project being evaluated:

³⁰ Makedon, V. V., Kholod, O. H., & Yarmolenko, L. I. (2023). The model for assessing the competitiveness of high-tech enterprises on the basis of the formation of key competences. *Academic Review*, 2(59), 75–89. <https://doi.org/10.32342/2074-5354-2023-2-59-5>

Mamchur, R., Minochkina, O., Ianushevych, I., & Khrystenko, L. (2023). *Id.*

$$X_{1j}^{ip} = [\lambda_j] \cdot \begin{cases} 1, \text{ if } X1_{2j}^{ip} - X2_{2j}^p > 0 \\ X1_{2j}^{ip} \\ 0, \text{ if } X1_{2j}^{ip} - X2_{2j}^p = 0 \\ X1_{2j}^{ip} \\ -1, \text{ if } X1_{2j}^{ip} - X2_{2j}^p < 0, \text{ or} \\ X1_{2j}^{ip} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

Next, for \tilde{X}^i , switch to the interval [0;1]:

$$\tilde{X}^i = \frac{\sum_{p=1}^N \sum_{j=1}^K X_{1j}^{ip}}{N + K} \quad (3)$$

To ensure effective interaction between public institutions and the private sector in the implementation of investment strategies aimed at achieving sustainable development goals, it is advisable to apply a decision-making model that takes into account the variability of the external economic environment.³¹ Taking into account the approaches of game theory, such a model allows to formalize the process of coordination of the interests of the state and business through a set of possible strategic scenarios. $\{X, \Theta, F\}$, (4)

The decision-making matrix is presented in Table 3.4, where f_{kj} is the index of profitability of the k -th investment project at the j -th state of the economic environment.

Since in our case the evaluation functionality f_{kj} is used to optimize profitability, it is defined in the form F^+ :

$$F = F^+ = \{f_{kj}\}, \quad (5)$$

i.e., the valuation functional F has a positive ingredient:

³¹ Tamara, A. (2024). Investment strategy in capital market. *Jurnal Ekonomi, Manajemen, Bisnis dan Akuntansi*, 1(1), 79–84. <https://doi.org/10.70963/jemba.v1i1.58>

$$\max_{x_k \in X} \{f_{kj}\} \tag{6}$$

Table 4. Matrix model of reconciliation of interests of the state and business when choosing an investment strategy in a changing economic environment

Investment strategy	State of the economic environment			
	Economic environment - option 1	Economic environment - option 2	...	Economic environment - option <i>n</i>
Strategy 1: public-private co-financing	f_{11}	f_{12}	...	f_{1n}
Strategy 2: institutional participation of business in government initiatives	f_{21}	f_{22}	...	f_{2n}
...
Strategy <i>k</i> : targeted partnerships in the field of sustainable development	f_{m1}	f_{m2}	...	f_{mn}

Source: developed by the authors

Stage two. As part of the formalization of the tools for strategic interaction between government institutions and business structures to ensure the goals of sustainable development, cash flows were forecasted in accordance with the selected investment strategies. The forecast covers variable scenarios of economic functioning - conditionally stable, progressive-positive, and crisis-negative. Taking into account the peculiarities of state regulation and private capital participation, tax revenues in the form of VAT are interpreted as a component of the cost of the resource base (materials and equipment), which is accordingly taken into account in the forecasted volume of

product sales (Tables 5, 6).

Table 5. Dynamics of projected cash flows under Project 1 Strengthening investment cooperation in the field of public-private partnership (UAH million) in the period 2025-2029

Type of economic environment	Indicators	2025	2026	2027	2028	2029
Stable	Investment expenses	200	0	0	0	0
	Operating expenses (before depreciation and amortization)	7200	7350	7350	7350	7350
	Tax deductions	440	470	470	470	470
	Total expenses	7840	7820	7820	7820	7820
	Revenues from sales (excluding VAT)	9100	9200	9200	9200	9200
	Depreciation and amortization expense	20	25	25	25	25
Favorable	Investment expenses	200	0	0	0	0
	Operating expenses (before depreciation and amortization)	6900	7000	7000	7000	7000
	Tax deductions	470	495	495	495	495
	Total expenses	7370	7495	7495	7495	7495
	Revenues from sales (excluding VAT)	8900	9050	9050	9050	9050
	Depreciation and amortization expense	20	25	25	25	25
Unfavorable	Investment expenses	200	0	0	0	0

ble	Operating expenses (before depreciation and amortization)	7800	7900	7900	7900	7900
	Tax deductions	410	435	435	435	435
	Total expenses	8410	8335	8335	8335	8335
	Revenues from sales (excluding VAT)	9300	9400	9400	9400	9400
	Depreciation and amortization expense	20	25	25	25	25

Source: calculated by the authors

Table 6. Dynamics of cash flows under Project 2. Expansion of environmental energy infrastructure for public-private partnership for the period 2025-2029 (UAH million)

Type of economic environment	Indicators	2025	2026	2027	2028	2029
Stable	Capital investments	180	-	-	-	-
	Operating expenses without depreciation and amortization	4600	6080	6080	6080	6080
	Income tax on the profit	290	430	450	450	450
	Total expenses	4970	6510	6530	6530	6530
	Revenue	570	7650	7650	7650	7650

	from sales (excluding VAT)	0				
	Depreciation and amortization	11	15	15	15	15
	Total cash flow from operations	5711	7665	7665	7665	7665
	Capital investments	180	-	-	-	-
	Operating expenses before depreciation and amortization	4370	5770	5770	5770	5770
	Income tax expense	310	410	430	430	430
Favorable	Total expenses	4860	6180	6200	6200	6200
	Revenue from sales (excluding VAT)	5500	7380	7380	7380	7380
	Depreciation and amortization	11	15	15	15	15
	Total cash flow from operations	5511	7395	7395	7395	7395

Unfavorable	Capital investments	180	-	-	-	-
	Operating expenses before depreciation and amortization	4840	6410	6410	6410	6410
	Income tax expense	270	390	410	410	410
	Total expenses	5290	6800	6820	6820	6820
	Revenue from sales (excluding VAT)	6000	8000	8000	8000	8000
	Depreciation and amortization	11	15	15	15	15
	Total cash flow from operations	6011	8015	8015	8015	8015

Source: calculated by the authors

Since the initial investments under Project 1 Creation of Intelligent Energy Infrastructure in the Framework of Public-Private Partnership and Project 2 "Modernization of Renewable Energy Supply Systems for Sustainable Development" do not exceed the amount of expected cash flows throughout the forecast period (2025-2029), the financial fragility ratio for both investment initiatives is zero. This situation indicates a minimal level of threat from the shortage of working capital at the implementation stage. At the same time, the risk weighting factor for the macroeconomic environment for the projects is estimated at 8.0, while the weighting of the potential illiquidity of the private business structure is 1.5, which confirms the predominance of external factors in modeling sustainable development.

The results of discounting cash flows showed that the integral index of profitability for Project 1 in the case of a stable economic situation is 1.1823; in a favorable economic environment it will be 1.1954; in the case of unfavorable macroeconomic conditions - 1.1692. Similarly, for Project 2, the following was calculated: the index of profitability in a stable situation is 1.1745, in a positive scenario, it will be 1.1896, and in the case of negative external factors, it will be 1.1613. Taking into account the obtained indicators and the level of riskiness of the scenarios, a decision matrix within the game model was built (Table 7).

Table 7. Decision matrix for choosing the optimal investment strategy under different economic scenarios

Investment project	Stable	Favorable	Unfavorable
Project 1: Energy efficient innovations in municipal infrastructure	1.1823	1.1954	1.1692
Project 2: Sustainable development through modernization of energy exchange systems	1.1745	1.1896	1.1613

Source: calculated by the authors

In the absence of reliable information on the probability of a certain economic scenario, it is advisable to apply an approach based on the Bernoulli-Laplace criterion. Within the framework of the proposed model, this criterion will involve the selection of a decision option $x_{ko} \in X$, which provides the maximum possible average result for all equally probable options for the economic situation.

$$B^+(x_{ko}, p) = \max_{x_k \in X} \left[\sum_{j=1}^n p_j \cdot f_{kj}^+ \right] \quad (7)$$

Thus, based on the assessment, it is advisable to recommend the investment initiative set out in Project 1 for implementation. The proposed methodology for assessing the economic feasibility of investments for partnerships between public and private entities is aimed at systematically addressing a number of key issues, namely:

- ensuring an integrated assessment of the effectiveness of the investment area in terms of its impact on the overall investment program;
- taking into account uncertainty and related risks inherent in the market environment;
- forming a balanced and diversified portfolio of investment strategies;

- adaptation to changing macroeconomic conditions.

5. DISCUSSION

The obtained scientific results revealed both coincidences and significant differences that emphasize the uniqueness and scientific value of the current research. In particular, the findings on the benefits of project investment and the role of public-business interaction confirm the opinion expressed by Wijaya et al.,³² who focused on the effectiveness of government guarantees, concessional lending, and institutional coordination. At the same time, compared to these studies, our work offers a formalized methodology for assessing the effectiveness of investment strategies based on a generalized financial sustainability index adapted to the specifics of the Ukrainian macroeconomic environment. In contrast to the concept of the life cycle of investment activity proposed in Baffo et al.,³³ which is mainly general, our methodological approach includes a deep mathematical formalization. It allows us to model investment scenarios taking into account game mechanisms and Bernoulli-Laplace functionalities, providing not only theoretical but also practical justification for choosing a strategy under uncertainty. This is confirmed by the results of cash flow simulations shown in Tables 5-7.

A critical review of the studies by Sinaj et al.³⁴ and Meuleman³⁵ emphasizes the importance of transparency, social responsibility, and trust in institutions in ensuring effective cooperation between sectors. At the same time, these works do not contain tools for quantifying the effect of public-private partnerships. The approach justified in this paper addresses this gap by offering a new system of financial sustainability indicators that is updated in real time and allows for the evaluation of investment portfolios in a dynamic environment. Our findings do not deny, but rather complement the ideas of Davidenko et al.³⁶ and Belu Manescu³⁷ on the need for a sectoral approach to investment. However, unlike existing works, authors introduce financial flexibility and risk parameters into the model, which allows us to more accurately assess the efficiency of sectoral investments, and the calculated financial fragility ratios for different scenarios demonstrate the advantage of projects with clear state participation as a guarantor. The peculiarity of our approach is the integration of various strategic models into a single logical and structural framework. Meanwhile, previous studies, such as McCaffrey and Poitiers,³⁸ focus mainly on the resource aspect or institutional conditions, without offering a comprehensive consideration of risks, financial

³² Wijaya, F., Waspada, I., & Sari, M. (2024). *Id.*

³³ Baffo, I., Leonardi, M., D'Alberti, V., & Petrillo, A. (2024). *Id.*

³⁴ Sinaj, Z., Vela, F., & Shaip, G. (2024). *Id.*

³⁵ Meuleman, L. (2021). *Id.*

³⁶ Davidenko, L., Titkov, A., Sherimova, N., & Beisembina, A. (2025). *Id.*

³⁷ Belu Manescu, C. (2024). *Id.*

³⁸ McCaffrey, C., & Poitiers, N. F. (2024). *Id.*

performance, and macroeconomic impact. Our paper presents a systematization of a number of investment strategies as a new framework for linking the elements of the synergistic model.

From a practical point of view, the results of the current study can be used in the process of public investment planning, in particular by institutionalizing the strategic alignment model. The proposed matrix model, based on financial indicators and logical orientation functions, can be easily adapted to the needs of a number of government agencies and regional administrations. These issues can help to improve the accuracy of forecasting the effectiveness of public-private partnerships, especially in the context of post-war economic recovery programs.

In addition, the paper expands the approach to cash flow forecasting by including inter-scenario variability: stable, favorable, and unfavorable economic environments. In this direction, the degree of uncertainty in strategic decision-making will be reduced. This aspect has been little studied in previous works, where scenario modeling is rarely combined with econometric analysis in the same methodological field. Our work makes a significant contribution to the scientific understanding of investment interactions, as it offers not only a conceptual framework but also an instrumental model that allows for informed decision-making under conditions of limited resources and high levels of uncertainty.

CONCLUSION

6.

It has been established that each investment strategy that can be used in the format of public-private partnerships plays a specific role in creating favorable conditions for attracting financial, managerial and technological resources. The functions of the state and the private sector within the framework of the respective strategic models are investigated, and specific implementation mechanisms are identified, from concession agreements to institutional deregulation and investment planning. Specific projected results for each strategy are identified, among which the most significant are multiplier effects, innovative renewal, increased added value, technological transformation, and minimization of social and economic threats in adverse conditions. The author proposes a standardized model of predicted results based on a comprehensive comparative table of characteristics, which makes it possible to select the most effective strategies in accordance with the goals of socio-economic progress.

It is established that effective cooperation between government agencies and business structures is carried out through a combination of mechanisms: targeted tax preferences, government guarantees, targeted project lending, and the creation of joint initiatives. The stability indicators of project strategies are studied, taking into account the risk of asset loss, delays in implementation, institutional burden, the amount of external support and the potential for reorganization of the capital structure. The use of project financing as the main format for the implementation of public-private investments in industries with a high level of strategic importance, in particular in

digital transformation, renewable energy and production modernization, is proposed.

The author substantiates the issue of attracting an investment initiative to the target portfolio by first determining the dynamics of the main indicators of financial stability, which allows reducing liquidity risks and ensuring predictable capitalization. The influence of different scenarios: stable, positive and crisis on the financial flows of public-private partnership projects is studied, on the basis of which the aggregate indices of profitability are analyzed with regard to discounting. The use of the Bernoulli-Laplace criterion for decision-making under conditions of uncertainty is substantiated, which made it possible to recommend the project with the highest average level of profitability for implementation. A matrix model for harmonizing the interests of the state and business based on an optimization function has been developed, which makes it possible to adapt strategies to changing environmental conditions.

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